

Manual annotations of SMB scenes : Pattern analysis

following <https://doi.org/10.1145/2427116.2427117>

Using maps from <https://nesmaps.com/maps/SuperMarioBrothers/SuperMarioBrothers.html>

Level segmentation procedure - setting up the env

- 1- Create a virtual env
- 2- Install stable-retro following the [dev installation guide](#)
- 3- Clone [mario dataset](#) + [mario.stimuli](#) through datalad
- 4- To have access to the spreadsheet with all the values regarding the segmentation:
 - 1- Go inside the mario directory
 - 2- Make sure to be using the [events branch](#): `git checkout events`
 - 3- `cd code/scenes/`
 - 4- open and edit `scenes_mastersheet.csv` (see next slide)

Level segmentation procedure - doing the thing !

5- Proceed to the segmentation of the level in this GSlides

6- For every segmented scene, annotate the content based on the different game patterns as defined in Table 1 of [Dahlskog & Togelius \(2012\)](#)

7- Add the info about the content of the scene in the scenes_mastersheet.csv

8- To get the Entry point and the Exit point of the scene:

1- Open the GUI: `cd stable-retro` and `./gym-retro-integration`

2- Load game (select the rom.nes file in the mario.stimuli/SuperMarioBros-Nes directory)

3- Load state... Use to select a specific state/level

4- To see the value: Window/Show scenario info... in the GUI

5- Look for: level_layout; player_x_posHi; player_x_posLo

6- To get the actual value for Entry/Exit point: $\text{player_x_posHi} * 256 + \text{player_x_posLo}$

Level annotation procedure - validating the thing !

To make sure the annotations make sense for all the segmented scenes, one proposition is to visualize the gameplays across trials and participants for each scene.

1- Make sure you ran `datalad get sub*/ses*/func/*event*` and `datalad get sub*/ses*/gamelogs/*bk2`

2- Run the `clip_extractor.py` script to segment the gameplays in scene:

```
python clip_extractor.py --datapath <path_to_bids_dataset> --output <path_to_save_outputs> --clip_extension mp4
```

3- Check if the annotations we have done bellow watch what is happening in the scenes. Add your observation to this google slides for each corresponding level

w111

Scene 0 :
- Beginning

Scene 1 :
- Enemy
- 2-path
- Risk/reward
- Roof

Scene 2 :
- Empty valley

Scene 3 :
- Enemy valley
- Enemy

Scene 4 :
- Enemy valley
- 2-hord

Scene 5 :
- Gap
- 2-path

Scene 6 :
- 3-path
- Risk/reward
- 2-hord

Scene 7 :
- Gap
- 3-path
- Risk/reward
- 2-hord

Scene 8 :
- 3-path
- Risk/reward
- 2-hord
- Enemy

Scene 9 :
- 3-path
- Risk/reward
- 4-horde

Scene 10 :
- Empty stair valley
- Stair up

Scene 11 :
- Gap stair valley

Scene 13 :
- 2-path
- 2-horde
- R/R
- Roof

Scene 14 :
- Stair up
- Flagpole

Scene 12 :
- Reward

w112

Scene 0 :
 - 2-hord
 - 2-path
 - Risk-reward

Scene 1 :
 - Enemy stair valley
 - 2-path
 - Risk-reward

Scene 2 :
 - 2-hord
 - 2-path
 - Risk-reward
 - Roof

Scene 3 :
 - 3-hord
 - Reward
 - Roof

Scene 4 :
 - Enemy
 - 2-hord
 - 3-path
 - Risk-reward
 - Roof

Scene 5 :
 - Gap
 - 2-path
 - Reward

Scene 6 :
 - 3-hord
 - Enemy valley
 - Pipe valley

Scene 8 :
 - Pillar gap

Scene 9 :
 - Stair up
 - 2-hord
 - Enemy
 - 2-path
 - Gap
 - Moving platform

Scene 10 :
 - Risk/Reward
 - Gap
 - Moving platform
 - Roof

Scene 11 :
 - Stair up
 - Flagpole

Scene 7 :
 - Reward

w1l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
- Beginning	- Variable gaps	- 2-Path - Enemy - Variable gaps	- 2-horde - Gap	- Variable gaps - 2-path - Moving platform - Risk/Reward	- Variable gaps - 2-path - Gap enemy	- Variable gaps - Moving platform	- Variable gaps - 2-horde - Gap enemy	- Multiple gaps	- Moving platform - Enemy	- Stair up - Flagpole

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WORLD 1-3

SUPER MARIO BROS.
©1988 NINTENDO

LEGEND

- Com
- Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
- Little Goomba
- Koopa Troopa
- Koopa Paratroopa

w211

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
- Beginning	- 2-path - Stairs up - Roof	- 2-path - 2-hord - Risk/Reward - Enemy stairs valley	- Enemy valley - 2-hord	- 2-hord - 3-path - Risk/Reward - Enemy - Roof	- 3-hord - 2-path - Risk/Reward	- 3-hord - 3-path - Roof	- Bonus zone - Moving platform	- 2-path - enemy - gap	- bonus zone	- Gap - enemy	- Enemy valley - Empty valley - 2-path - Risk/Reward	- gap - enemy	- gap - enemy	- 4-hord - 2-path - risk/reward	- enemy - 2-path - roof	- flagpole

w2l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beginning - Stair up - Gap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - Risk/Reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - Variable gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - Multiple gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - Stairs down 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stairs up - Flagpole

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SUPER MARIO BROS.
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Game
 Super Mario Bros.
 Donkey Kong

w3l1

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
- Beginning	- 2-hord - Risk/reward - Roof - 2 path	- Enemy valley - Gap	- 3-hord enemy valley - Roof - 2-path	- Bonus zone	- stairs up - 3-hord - gap - risk/reward	- 2-hord - Enemy valley - 2-path - Risk/reward - Stair down	- 3-path - Risk/reward - Enemy - Roof	- 3-path - Stairs up - 2-hord - Gap	- Bonus zone	- 3-hord - Enemy - 3-path - Risk/reward - Roof	- Roof - Enemy - 3-hord - Gap	- 2-hord - Stairs up - Flagpole

w3l2

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
- Beginning - Enemy	- 3-hord	- 3-hord	- 2-hord	- Empty valley	- Risk/Reward - Enemy valley - 3-hord -	- Roof valley - Risk/Reward gap	- Enemy	- Enemy	- 3-hord - Multiple gaps	- Enemy - 3-hord	- 2-hord	- 3-hord	- Enemy - 3-hord	- 3-hord - Stairs up - Flagpole

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SUPER MARIO BROS.
NINTENDO NINTENDO

LEGEND

- ☐ Coin
- 👾 Flagpole
- 👾 Piranha Fire Flower
- 👾 Starman
- 👾 Little Goomba
- 👾 Koopa Troopa
- 👾 Koopa Paratroopa
- 👾 Piranha Plant

w3|3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
- Beginning	- Gap - Enemy	- Moving platform - Variable gaps	- Gap - Risk/Reward - Enemy - 2-path	- Moving platform - gap	- Enemy - 2-path	- Moving platforms - Variable gaps	- Moving platforms - Variable gaps - 2-path	- Gap enemy	- 2-hord	- Moving platforms - Variable gaps - Flagpole

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WORLD 3-3
 ©1985 NINTENDO

LEGEND
 Coin
 Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
 Little Goomba
 Koopa Troopa
 Koopa Paratroopa

w4l1

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
- Beginning	- Enemy - Risk/Reward - gap	- Enemy	- enemy - gap -	- 2-path - risk/reward	- Enemy - valley	- Pipe valley	- Gap - 3-path - Risk/reward - Enemy - Roof	- Bonus zone - Reward	- Variable gaps - Enemy	- Gap - enemy - 2-hord	- Stairs up - flagpole

w4l2

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beginning - Variable gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hor d roof 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-pat h - Risk/Reward - Moving platform - Gap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy valley - Roof valley - 2-pat h 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonus zone - Stairs up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonus zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roofv alley - Risk/Reward - 2-pat h 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonus zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-hor d - Enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-pat h - moving platfo rms - risk/r eward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy valley - Pipe valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stairs up - moving platfo rms - multi ple gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - risk/r eward - 2-hor d - roof - Stairs up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enem y valley gap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stairs up - Flagpole 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonu s zone

w4l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
- beginning	- Variable gaps - 2-hord	- Gap enemy - 2-path - variable gap	- 2-path - reward - moving platform - Variable gaps	- Moving platforms - Variable gaps - 2-path	- enemy - 3-path - Variable gaps	- Variable gaps - moving platforms	- Variable gaps - moving platforms	- Variable gaps - moving platforms	- Variable gaps - 2 path	- Variable gaps - moving platforms - flagpole

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WORLD 4-3

SUPER MARIO BROS.
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LEGEND

- Coin
- Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
- Koopa Troopa
- Koopa Paratroopa

w5l1

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
- beginning	- enemy - 3-hord	- 3-hord	- 2-hord - gap - pipe valley	- enemy - 3-hord	- 3-hord	- enemy - gap - reward - 2-path	- 3-hord - gap - enemy	- 3-hord - enemy	- 3-hord	- 2-hord - gap - reward - enemy	- bonus zone	- enemy - 2 hord	- stairs up - flagpole

w5l2

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
- beginning	- stairs up - enemy	- gap - 3-path - reward	- enemy - stairs up	- 2-hord - stairs up - gap	- bonus zone (aquaworld)	- 2-path - enemy	- bonus zone (sky) - moving platform	- 2-path - gap	- enemy	- 3-path - enemy - risk/reward - gap - roof valley	- 3-hord - risk/reward	- gap - 2-path - enemy - 2-hord	- 2-hord - 2-path - risk/reward - Variable gaps	- Gap - enemy - multiple gaps - stairs-up - flagpole

w5l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
- beginning	- Variable gaps - enemy	- Multiple gaps - enemy	- gaps - 2 hord - enemy - 2-path	- Variable gaps - enemy - moving platform - 2 path - reward	- Variable gaps - Gap enemy	- Variable gaps - enemy - moving platform	- Variable gaps - Gap enemy	- Variable gaps - enemy -	- moving platform - enemy	- stairs-up - flagpole

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WORLD 5-3

SUPER MARIO BROS.
© 1985 NINTENDO

LEGEND

- Coin
- Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
- Little Goomba
- Koopa Troopa
- Koopa Paratroopa
- Bullet Bill

w6l1

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
- beginning	- gap - enemy - 2-hord -	- stairs up - 2-path - risk/reward - enemy - Variable gaps	- gap - enemy	- stairs up - gap - enemy	- stairs up - enemy - risk/reward - gap	- enemy	- stairs up - reward - enemy - roof - Variable gaps	- stairs up - gap - enemy	- gap - enemy	- stairs up - gap - flagpole - enemy

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- LEGEND
- Coin
 - Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
 - 1 up Mushroom
 - Lakitu
 - Spiny
 - Spiny's Egg
 - Piranha Plant

w6l2

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
- beginnig - 2-path	- Roof valley - 2-path	- bonus zone	- Roof valley	- risk/reward - roof valley	- roof valley	- bonus zone (waterworld)	- roof valley - 2-path	- bonus zone (clouds) - moving platform	- pipe valley - enemy	- roof valley - 2-path	- 2-path - gap - enemy	- pipe wally - 2-path	- multiple gaps - risk/reward - stairs up - 3 path	- 3-path - roof valley	- bonus zone - reward	- pipe valley - stairs up - 3 hord	- staur - flagpole - enemy

w6l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
- beginning	- Variable gaps	- Variable gaps - moving platform	- Variable gaps - moving platform - 2-path	- risk/reward - Variable gaps - moving platform	- Variable gaps - moving platform	- Variable gaps - enemy	- Variable gaps - moving platform - enemy	- Variable gaps - moving platform	- gap - flagpole

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WORLD 6-3

SUPER MARIO BROS.
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LEGEND

- Coin
- Map: Mushroom or Fire Flower
- Bullet Bill

w711

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - beginning enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - risk/reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roof valley - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - roof - gap - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-path - enemy - Roof valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - risk/reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bonus zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - empty valley - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - empty valley - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-path - roof valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-path - enemy valley - gap - stairs up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stairs up - enemy - flagpole

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- LEGEND
- Coin
 - 1 up Mushroom
 - ☄ Bullet Bill
 - ♄ Buzzy Beetle
 - 👤 Koopa Troopa
 - 👤 Koopa Paratroopa
 - 🌿 Piranha Plant
 - 👤 The Hammer Brothers

w713

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - beginning gap - stairs up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy risk/reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - Variable gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable gaps - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - stairs down 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stairs up - flagpole

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w8l1

	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
enemy 3-hord	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - risk/reward - pipe valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pipe valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bonus zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hord - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy - 3-hord 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hord 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hord - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roof valley - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-hord - Variable gaps - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reward - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable gaps - 2-hord 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hord - Pillar gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy - 3-hord 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -

w8l2

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - beginning enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - stairs up - multiple gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-path enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - multiple gaps - reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - multiple gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-hor d gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gap enemy - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - risk/reward - roof - 2 path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - roof - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-hor d enemy valley - roof - 2-path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - empty valley - gap enemy - enemy valley - pipe valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pipe valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bonus zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-hor d Variable gaps - Gap enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2-hor d enemy valley - stairs up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gap enemy - stairs up - Variable gap - flagpole

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- WORLD 0-2
- LEGEND
- Coin
 - Magic Mushroom or Fire Flower
 - Redret Pit
 - Dizzy Beeble
 - Lakitu
 - Little Goomba
 - Wario Paratroopa
 - Piranha Plant
 - Spiny
 - Spiny's Egg

w8l3

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - beginning enemy - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - empty valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-path - enemy - gap - risk/reward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stairs down - gap - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - empty valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-path - risk/reward - enemy - Pillar gap - Roof valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enemy valley - valley 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stairs up - multiple gaps - flagpole

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- Code
- Clips: Mushroom at the Tower
- Level 11
- Koopa Paratroopa
- Goomba
- The Hammer Brothers